

Disciplinary Commons in TCS

Teaching Algorithms and Automata on a Degree Apprenticeship Programme in Wales

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This portfolio gives an overview of the Algorithms and Automata module taught at Swansea University in the academic years 2022/23 and 2023/24. It explores the specifics of teaching computational thinking for a degree apprenticeship programme. The key aspect that distinguishes this module from similar modules taught as a part of traditional computer science / software engineering degrees, is the particularly varied background of our students. While some students are joining the programme straight from school, others have substantial work experience in software engineering and related areas. This diversified background shapes the module and impacts the choice of topics taught as well as their depth. This portfolio reflects upon the choices made with respect to the curriculum, teaching methods and assessment.

The portfolio consists of 4 parts:

- Section 1 (**Context**) describes how the module fits within the whole programme.
- Section 2 (**Content**) gives an overview of the topics taught as well as the structure of the module.
- Section 3 (**Teaching Philosophy and Methods**) explores the teaching philosophy that I follow when teaching this module.
- Section 4 (**Student Learning and Assessment**) gives an overview of assessment approaches that I use as well as some reflection on how these can be improved.

1 Context

CSF206 Algorithms and Automata is a core second-year module in a three-year long Degree Apprenticeship (DA) in Applied Software Engineering Programme, developed on the basis of the CS-270 Algorithms and CS-175 Modelling Computing Systems modules taught at a regular BSc Computer Science Programme at Swansea University. The CSF206 curriculum is modified to cater for the DA students, who have diverse experiences prior to starting the programme. The official capacity for a student cohort each year is 50 people.

1.1 The Degree Apprenticeship Programme

The DA programme¹ consists of 22 modules delivered over three years (see fig. 1). It allows employees of companies across Wales to gain a degree in Software Engineering while being in full-time

¹Information about the DA programme: <https://www.swansea.ac.uk/undergraduate/courses/maths-comp-sci/computer-science/bsc-applied-software-engineering/>

Figure 1: Degree Apprenticeship Structure

employment. A typical academic year consists of 3 terms, each lasting 12 weeks. Students are expected to complete 2 taught modules each term, while simultaneously working on their work-based portfolio module (Years 1 and 2) or their final year project (Year 3). Work-based portfolios complement taught modules and allow our students to apply what they learn in the context of their workplace.

1.2 Algorithms and Automata within the DA

CSF206 is a 15-credit module, which is currently standard for all taught modules on the DA.

1.2.1 Objectives and Outcomes

The key **objective** of Algorithms and Automata is to help the students to develop transferable skills of abstract modelling, formal reasoning, computational thinking, and problem solving.

As stated in the module proforma, the expected **outcomes** of this module are the following:

- Students will be familiar with the use of automata for modelling computing systems.
- Students will appreciate the idea of analysing an algorithm to determine its efficiency.
- Students will be familiar with, and be able to use, basic data structures.
- Students will know and understand standard sorting and searching algorithms and be able to comment on their relative performance.

To understand why these particular objectives and outcomes are useful for a software engineering student, one needs to understand the context of the DA programme. This programme is primarily aimed at people who work in the area of software engineering and digital technology but do not

have an official software engineering qualification. As such, many (but not all) are expected to have a reasonable programming background and the aim of this module is to enhance their problem solving capabilities, help them understand how their choices of specific data structures / algorithms impact the efficiency of their programs, etc.

The **emphasis** in this module is on abstraction, computational thinking and problem solving over applied programming. In fact, it does not include any programming exercises but rather discusses general patterns and approaches in algorithms and automata, using pseudocode to avoid tying the module content to a specific programming language. This contrasts with the majority of the algorithms-related modules discussed within the Disciplinary Commons, which normally include a programming component.

One may argue that focusing on theory over implementation may not be suitable for an *Applied* Software Engineering degree. However, a counterargument is that students working as software engineers will likely gain extensive hands-on experience with programming, data structures, and algorithms in their daily work. This allows the academic programme to focus developing more creative problem-solving abilities and addressing deeper questions about algorithmic complexity and performance of algorithms. The primary objective of this module is to encourage students to think more broadly and approach challenges with greater creativity and insight.

1.2.2 CSF206 and Other Modules

Although there are no formal prerequisites to CSF206, it builds upon the content taught in CSF101/CSF102 Programming 1 and 2, CSF105 Computer Science Concepts, and CSF106 Discrete Mathematics. CSF206 also creates a useful base for some of the following modules, namely CSF209 Applied Software Testing, CSF307 Advanced Object Oriented Programming, and CSF325 Artificial Intelligence.

1.2.3 Work-Based Component

Similarly to other taught second-year modules, CSF206 is accompanied by work-based assignments. They are based on the content of this module and contribute towards a year-long 30-credit module (CSF200 Work-Based Portfolio 2). Students are required to complete two work-based assignments per term, one for each module taught during that term.

Given the programme's tight schedule, the essential content needed to complete these assignments is usually delivered by week 5 of the term. The assignments are intentionally broad, accommodating for the diverse industries in which our students work. The tasks are developed in cooperation with the Gower College, who oversee CSF200 and mark our students' submissions.

Automata is covered as the first topic in my module, so for the work-based assignment in CSF200 students apply their knowledge to model one of their workplace processes as an automaton from a user perspective. This process could be part of a computer system, business workflow, or a manual process – the choice is entirely up to a student, provided that their model is complex enough.

While subject module coordinators like myself are involved in the design of the work-based assessments for their respective modules and moderate the marking, they are not normally involved in the week-to-week running of the CSF200 module.

1.3 Schedule and Environment

The DA programme is delivered on Wednesdays 1pm-8pm on Swansea University Singleton Campus. A typical DA Wednesday follows this schedule:

1pm - Module A Lecture 1	4pm - Module B Lecture 2
2pm - Module B Lecture 1	5pm - break
3pm - Module A Lecture 2	6pm - 2 hour lab for both modules

Lectures take place in one of the Faraday building lecture rooms in Singleton Campus. A typical student cohort is between 15 and 30 students, while the room capacity is 60. The room is equipped with a whiteboard, a projector, and a document camera. This allows for a range of different approaches to presenting the teaching material.

Labs take place in a large computer lab designed to fit 120 students. Standard lab computers allow students to install a range of useful software programs. Students often bring their own devices to the labs as well. It allows them to work on the lab tasks outside of the contact hours.

Students from all year groups gather in a shared lab space on Wednesdays between 6pm and 8pm to work on their lab assignments. Using an online queuing system, they can conveniently ask for help or request sign-offs.

Using a shared space for all year groups allows DA lecturers to provide support more efficiently, addressing questions related not only to their own modules but also to other modules within the programme. This approach allows us to attend to the students faster. Additionally, by helping students with other modules, the lecturers get a better overview of the content taught across the programme. Working in the same space also improves the sense of community, as students in higher year groups also help their co-workers and friends from lower year groups.

The **Learning Management System** that Swansea University uses is Canvas. This is the main platform through which we interact with the students. Content is uploaded weekly at least a week in advance, giving students the opportunity to review it ahead of the lecture if they wish to do so. All slides are available in a digital format but printed handouts are used during lectures as they are an essential part of the lectures. All lectures are recorded via Panopto and uploaded to Canvas for easy access.

Additionally, we maintain a DA Discord server open to students from all year groups. It creates a greater sense of community as students from various year groups join discussions and share their experiences.

1.4 Student Context

The DA programme is primarily for individuals working in software engineering and digital technology who lack formal qualifications. However, the reality is that this course attracts a far more diverse demographic. Over time, the range of student backgrounds has significantly expanded, and this tendency toward greater diversification is expected to continue. Currently, the programme welcomes people with or without IT-related background, including those just starting their careers, individuals seeking career advancement, those aiming to change qualifications, or learners simply expand their knowledge and skills. The recent cohorts were also characterised by a broad age range: from 19-year-olds going up to early 60s.

The main **constraint** in teaching CSF206 is that some students do not always have the required mathematical background. The regular Computer Science / Software Engineering course offered by the Department requires ABB-BBB as does the DA programme. However, more often than not

the DA recognises prior experience. The application process includes interviews and aptitude tests, which assess applicants' competencies. This allows for a more inclusive approach, which widens participation, however, it means that mathematical skills in the cohort may vary. The knowledge gap is particularly noticeable when students start learning about computational complexity.

To cater for the diversity of backgrounds the modules on the programme need to be developed in a way that enables less experienced learners to follow at a required speed, while keeping more experienced learners engaged.

1.5 Lecturer Context

My background is in Pedagogy (BA in Pedagogy (2006) from Ternopil National Pedagogical University, Ukraine) and Theoretical Computer Science (PhD in Computer Science (2021) from Swansea University, Wales). Previously, I taught CSF206 in two different settings: online during the lockdown and in-person after that. This experiences informed my reflections, discussed in section 3.

2 Content

Within a 12 week long term, the students are expected to attend 20 lecture hours and 10 lab hours dedicated to Algorithms and Automata. As shown in Table 2, every week there are 2 lectures (50 min each), with the exception of the test weeks², when there is only 1 lecture. Hence, there are 30 formal contact hours, while the notional hours are 150.

As the name suggests, this module revolves around 2 major topics:

- key **automata** concepts, covered in weeks 1-4 (8 lecture hours, 4 lab hours, supplemented by a quick (max. 15 min) recap in week 6)
- **algorithms** and data structures, covered in weeks 5-11 (10 lecture hours, 6 lab hours, supplemented by 1 recap lecture in week 11)

2.1 A Walk Through the Module Content

Table 2 illustrated the broad range of topics covered in this module. Given the limited timeline, this breadth naturally limits the depth at which each topic can be explored. As a result, this module aims to provide a broad enough overview of the relevant topics during contact hours, while inspiring the students to explore more through independent study. The following sections give an insight into the content covered.

2.1.1 Automata

To avoid overwhelming students with the complexities of automata theory, we begin in a playful manner, introducing the fundamental concepts of automata through a number of puzzles and games. Interestingly, this approach has also been adapted and successfully used at earlier stages of education (see: [Teaching Them Early: Formal Methods in School](#)³).

²Each term students have 4 tests: 2 for Module A and 2 for Module B. Weeks 6, 7, 11 and 12 are test weeks.

³Moller, F., O'Reilly, L., Powell, S., Denner, C. (2021). Teaching Them Early: Formal Methods in School. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1301., pp.173-190, Springer

Week no.	No. of lectures	Topics covered	Labs	Assessments
1	2	Solving puzzles with LTS	Crossing the river puzzle	
2	2	Puzzles (continued) Modelling vending machines	Queen in a tower puzzle	
3	2	Copycat game Colourful winning strategies	LTS	Coursework 1 released
4	2	Modelling elevators Introduction to process algebra	Bisimulation colouring	
5	2	Data structures Introduction to program analysis	Data structures	Coursework 1 due
6	1	Recap of Automata (15 min) Growth of functions (35 min)	Big O part 1	
7	1	Big O	Big O part 2	Test1
8	2	Divide & Conquer: sorting, searching, and Master theorem	Sorting	Coursework 2 released
9	2	Greedy algorithms	Greedy algorithms	
10	2	Dynamic programming	Dynamic programming	Coursework 2 due
11	1	Recap of Algorithms		
12	1	Fun/guest lecture (optional)		Test2
		Total lecture hours: 20	Total lab hours: 10	

Table 2: Algorithms and Automata module overview

The first part of the module is highly interactive. Students are given various worksheets (e.g., see Appendix 4), which they use during the lectures to solve puzzles and/or apply the concepts that they are learning on the go. Here are the main concepts that are discussed in this part of the module:

- Modelling processes (labelled transition systems, computations and processes, language for describing processes, equality between processes) and distinguishing between them (bisimulation relations and bisimulation colourings).
- Logical properties and processes (the *mays* and *musts* of processes, modal logic for properties)
- Students are also shown this [UPPAAL demo](#)⁴ of a mini railway interlocking system as an example of a slightly more complex model than we have a chance to discuss in class.

2.1.2 Data Structures and Algorithms

The second part of the module begins with a lecture on **data structures**. At this point, the students have already covered data structures to a certain extent in CSF105 Computer Science Concepts and CSF102 Programming 2. The aim of my lecture is not necessarily to introduce new concepts – although this is done to a certain extent as well – but rather to aggregate the information scattered across other modules and present it in a structured way, supplemented by examples of real-world application. These real-world examples make the theoretical concepts more relatable for the students. Among the concepts that are covered in the lecture are the following:

- Basic data structures: arrays, linked lists
- Abstract data types vs data structures
- Abstract data types (linear, non-linear, hierarchical, general)
- Lists, stacks and queues
- Graphs and their representations
- Trees (binary trees, heaps, spanning trees)

Time constraints limit the depth to which certain topics can be covered, requiring omission of certain aspects. For instance, red-black trees or treaps are not covered. However, to encourage individual exploration of relevant topics, students are provided with links to additional online resources. Recognising that many students on the programme have limited experience with academic research papers, I prioritise articles/blog posts which aggregate information from multiple reliable sources and are written in a friendly and approachable way. The feedback received so far indicates that the students find these supplementary resources highly valuable.

Finally, the **algorithms** part begins with the introduction to program analysis, growth of functions and Big-O. Recognising that complexity of algorithms is a challenging topic to teach, it is covered over a span of three weeks. This extended timeline gives students more opportunity to absorb the relevant concepts and engage in additional practice, ensuring deeper understanding. Following this, the module explores various computational problems and looks at how different types of algorithms can be used to solve them.

⁴UPPAAL Demo: <https://youtu.be/IMHOaQyHqck>

- Divide and conquer algorithms
 - sorting: insertion sort, merge sort, quick sort
 - searching: binary search
 - simplified Master Theorem for algorithm analysis
- Greedy algorithms
 - greedy-choice property and optimal substructure property
 - Kruskal's algorithm
 - solving timetabling problems using greedy algorithms
- Dynamic programming
 - overlapping subproblems property
 - solving knapsack problems using dynamic programming

The general approach is straightforward: I present a computational problem and then ask the following questions:

- *How will you approach it (divide and conquer / greedy algorithm / dynamic programming)?*
- *What is the Big-O of your suggested algorithm?*
- *Can we do better? If yes, how? If not, why?*

2.2 Textbooks and Other Resources

This module is self-contained, providing all essential materials students need succeed. However, I encourage them to depend their understanding by exploring relevant textbooks⁵:

- Moller F., Struth G. (2013). *Modelling computing systems : mathematics for computer science*. 1st ed. Springer.
 - Chapter 11: Modelling Processes
 - Chapter 12: Distinguishing Between Processes
 - Chapter 13: Logical Properties of Processes
- Shaffer, C.A. (2001). *A Practical Introduction to Data Structures and Algorithm Analysis*. 2nd ed. Pearson.
 - Chapter 4: Lists, Stacks and Queues
 - Chapter 5: Binary Trees
 - Chapter 7: Graphs
- Cormen, T.H., Leiserson, C.E., Rivest, R.L. and Stein, C. (2009). *Introduction to Algorithms*. 3rd ed. MIT Press.
 - Part I Foundations (chapter 1: The Role of Algorithms in Computing, chapter 2: Getting Started, chapter 3: Growth of Functions, chapter: 4 Divide-and-Conquer)

⁵Books are listed in the order in which the relevant content is taught.

- Part II Sorting and Order Statistics (chapter 7: Quicksort)
 - Part IV Advanced Design and Analysis Techniques (chapter 15: Dynamic Programming, chapter 16: Greedy Algorithms)
 - Part VI Graph Algorithms (chapter 23: Minimum Spanning Trees)
- Bhargava, A.Y. (2016). *Grokking Algorithms: An illustrated guide for programmers and other curious people*. Manning, Shelter Island, NY.
 - Chapter 8: Greedy Algorithms
 - Chapter 9: Dynamic Programming

Using Cormen’s Introduction to Algorithms would be sufficient for teaching algorithms at a regular degree but taking into account the specifics of the DA, I found that supplementing that content with examples from *Grokking Algorithms* is beneficial. Those examples are particularly popular with the students. They make the content more engaging and accessible, especially for those who find the material challenging.

Additionally, I frequently incorporate props into my lectures, particularly when teaching concepts such as bisimulation colouring, recursion, and when working with puzzles. I also make use of various online resources to enhance the learning experience:

- **Online Graphviz Editor**: a simple web-based tool for graph visualisation;
- **Desmos Graph Calculator**: a useful online tool for visualising the growth of functions. I find it particularly useful when covering complexity: it gives me an quick and easy way to explain what an *upper* or a *lower* bound of a function is;
- **Data Structures Visualisation Tool** by David Galles is a great visual tool to help students understand not only how to work with various data structures but also how various algorithms run;
- **AlgoRythmics**: a Youtube channel, which uses dances to explain how various algorithms work in playful manner.
- **Brilliant**: a good collection of resources in computer science (and other subjects), which students can use as supplementary material for their individual development;
- **Panopto**: video recording software.
- **Slido**: Q&A and polling platform;
- **Draw.io**: a free open source cross-platform graph drawing software;
- **Ziteboard**: an online whiteboard.

3 Teaching Philosophy and Methods

The general philosophy is **teaching by intuition** rather than direct instruction, which promotes engagement and development of analytical and critical skills. Considering the varied skill levels among my students, presenting the content in a highly academic manner can sometimes be overwhelming for them. To address this, I adopt a playful approach, introducing concepts through puzzles and real-life problems.

3.1 Teaching Methods

My **lectures** are not always delivered in a traditional fashion. For instance, during the first couple of Automata lectures students solve several puzzles without prior guidance. They are given 5-10 minutes to work on solutions independently before the whole class discusses their strategies and explores ways to refine and improve them. These discussions naturally lead to the notion of *state*. Following that, *labelled transition systems* are introduced as a tool which can help solving certain kind of puzzles. These puzzles increase in complexity, with each new attempt reinforcing the underlying approach and helping students build a stronger problem-solving skills.

Algorithms are introduced in a similar manner, starting with basic theoretical concepts that are reinforced by the use of props and practical problem-solving exercises. The emphasis during discussions is on understanding how to approach specific problems algorithmically, rather than on programming. The aim is not to implement an algorithm in a specific programming language but rather get an intuitive understanding of how to approach a variety of computational problems. For instance, playing cards are used to visualise recursive sorting:

- Students are given a selection of unsorted cards and they are instructed to take one and pass the remaining unsorted cards to their neighbour.
- When the final card is handed out it represents a sorted list with 1 element in it.
- This sorted list is then passed to the previous person, who inserts their own card into the correct position in the sorted list.
- This continues until the list gets fully sorted.

Everything in this module is built on a principle of reinforcement. For instance, to explain how greedy algorithms work, students are given several simple instances of the Knapsack problem to solve. The first problem is done in such a way, that a simple greedy approach works and gives an optimal solution. The following problems get harder and eventually lead the students to the understanding that greedy algorithms do work but there is no guarantee that the solution that they provide is always optimal. Later, when dynamic programming is introduced, the Knapsack problem is revisited, and students can understand the benefits of this approach over greedy algorithms.

Weekly **lab sessions** are aimed to supplement the material taught in the respective week. Students are encouraged to work in pairs/small groups and solve small tasks that test their understanding of the newly learnt topic. Working in groups sparks discussions and develops critical thinking. I join these discussions afterwards to make sure that everyone is on the right track. An example lab task is presented in fig. 2.

Participation in the Disciplinary Commons inspired me to experiment by adding a couple of optional programming exercises alongside the usual labs. The motivation behind this decision stems from the fact that the current student cohorts are weaker in programming compared to the previous years and I aim to address this gap. A number of my students do not program in their professional roles. While the primary focus of this module remains to understand the abstract concepts and build from there, I am of the opinion that these optional programming assignments can help students to understand abstract concepts through practical implementation. Unfortunately, since these tasks were optional and students had a heavy workload, engagement was minimal. This raises the question of how effective optional exercises truly are and whether there are strategies that could be implemented to encourage the students to engage more fully with additional learning opportunities.

You're a treasure hunter who came across 5 rare artifacts, each with a different weight and market value. Your goal is to select the artifacts that you can carry home, without exceeding the weight limit of your luggage. The items you have to consider are:

Item	Weight	Value
Ancient Silver Chalice	2kg	£10,000
Ancient Stone Tablet	5kg	£40,000
Rare Meteorite Fragment	7kg	£60,000
Renaissance Sculpture	3kg	£30,000
Golden Inca Figurine	2kg	£20,000

You can only carry a total weight of 10kg. You want to find a set of items which maximises the value, but where the total weight is at most 10kg. Use **dynamic programming** to find a solution to this.

Figure 2: Example: Dynamic Programming Lab Task

3.2 Traditional Classroom vs Zoom

Each of the teaching modes have their advantages and disadvantages. My experience shows that in-person teaching of this module works better: it allows more interactivity in class, which makes students more engaged. There is a range of good techniques and tools that can be used online to boost engagement (Ziteboard, Slido, Kahoot, Mentimeter, etc.). Clearly, using cards to explain recursion as mentioned above is rather tricky in an online setting, so it can be substituted by a video⁶. While it may not be as engaging as actively participating in the process yourself, it still serves as an effective visual aid. **AlgoRythmics** dancing videos also serve as an engaging supplementary aid for understanding how various sorting and search algorithms work.

One can use resources like **Data Structures Visualisation Tool** and **Desmos Graph Calculator** in both settings. Since they are available to everyone, students can also explore them out in their own time, which is likely to enhance their understanding.

Zoom breakout rooms provide an effective way to split the class into smaller groups for brief discussions. This approach tends to appeal to students who might be too shy to share their thoughts with the the whole class. While it is possible to organise such group discussions in a traditional classroom setting, my experience suggests that they works slightly better online. The structured nature of breakout rooms seems to make the setup feel more organised as well.

4 Student Assessment

Summative assessment in this module are designed in alignment with the standard assessment framework of the DA programme. These assessments include the components outlined below, with their timeline illustrated in fig. 3.

- **Coursework 1** in Automata (**15%**, written) is released in week 3. The first part is usually a puzzle that needs to be solved using a labelled transition system. The second part is a bisimulation colouring task.
- **Mid-term test** in Automata (**30%**, written) covers topics taught in weeks 1 - 4. It is a timed, 1-hour-long test, consisting of a number of questions summing up to 25 marks.

⁶Visualisation of recursive insertion sort: <https://youtu.be/uuUons3WRwU>

- **Coursework 2** in Algorithms and Data Structures (**15%**, written) is released in week 7 and covers topics taught in weeks 5 - 8.
- **End-term test** in Algorithms and Data Structures (**30%**, written) covers topics taught in weeks 5 - 10. Similarly to the mid-term, this is a timed, 1-hour-long test, consisting of a number of questions summing up to 25 marks.
- **Labs (10%**, written with discussion) consist of a number of tasks that need to be solved within max. 2 weeks.

All tests undergo an internal review within the DA team and then are passed to an external reviewer from another university. Once tests are marked, 10% sample is moderated by an internal moderator.

Feedback in the labs is informal and verbal, whereas for courseworks it is formal and written. General feedback on courseworks is shared via a group announcement and individual feedback is provided via annotations and comments on Canvas. For tests, students receive general feedback through a group announcement. If a student requests additional feedback, a one-to-one meeting is arranged to review the test paper with them in detail.

Formative assessment is informal. During lectures and office hours it takes the form of group and one-to-one discussions. Additionally, Slido quizzes are used for ad-hoc assessment during lectures. Looking ahead, I intend to develop a number of practice quizzes on Canvas, which students will be able to complete in their own time. In the meantime, I guide students to use specific publicly available quizzes, e.g. the one offered by Brilliant⁷.

While lab tasks are designed to be a summative assessment, they also provide opportunities for formative assessment through individual and group discussions. I use lab sessions as an opportunity to steer my students in the right direction and identify potential gaps in their understanding. When I notice a common misunderstanding of a particular concept, I revisit that topic in the following week to ensure that any doubts are clarified and misconceptions are resolved.

Some Final Reflections

Participating in the Disciplinary Commons has provided valuable insights into how other lecturers design their courses, many of which incorporate active programming components. This has inspired me to consider introducing non-optional programming assignments into this module. However, my priority is to ensure that these additions do not overshadow the primary goal of helping students master the underlying theoretical concepts. The focus must remain on enabling students to solve computational problems effectively, regardless of the programming language they use, and to apply their understanding of algorithms and data structures to design computationally viable solutions.

One aspect to consider before adding programming components is the growing usage of generative AI by students. Should students use AI to solve programming exercises in this module, they may bypass the critical thinking required to understand the core concepts, and the purpose of these programming exercises as a valuable learning tool could be undermined. I believe, one needs to find

Figure 3: Assessment timeline

⁷<https://brilliant.org/practice/big-o-notation>

a careful balance between amount of programming and theory in a module like this to maximise educational value.

Another area of improvement I am exploring is making the module more relatable by presenting examples of automata theory, algorithms, and data structures that align with scenarios from students' workplaces. This connection to their professional environments could help students see the relevance of theoretical concepts and inspire greater engagement.

Overall, participating in the Disciplinary Commons has been an excellent platform for sharing ideas and learning from the experiences of others, offering fresh perspectives to refine and improve my teaching practices.

Appendix

CSF206 – Algorithms and Automata – Worksheet 2022/23

PUZZLE 1 – THE MAN-WOLF-GOAT-CABBAGE RIDDLE

A man needs to cross a river with

- a wolf,
- a goat, and
- a cabbage.

His boat is only large enough to carry himself and one of his three possessions, so he must transport these items one at a time. However, if he leaves the wolf and the goat together unattended, then the wolf will eat the goat; similarly, if he leaves the goat and the cabbage together unattended, then the goat will eat the cabbage. How can the man get across safely with his three items?

LABELLED TRANSITION SYSTEMS

This puzzle can be solved by modelling it by a **Labelled Transition System** (LTS), which consists of:

- **a set of states** represented pictorially as circles; and
- **a set of transitions** or arrows between states which are labelled by actions.

BACK TO THE RIDDLE...

- What are our states for this riddle?

Imagine you are on a high mountain looking down at the valley below. The current situation is a state.

If the man crosses the river, then we have a new state.

A state must capture everything that is relevant to the puzzle.

Discuss with a partner and write your ideas below:

What does our notion of state consist of?

What actions (transitions) can you do to get from one state to another?

Now we have our notion of states and actions we can create an LTS to represent the riddle.

Consider appropriate syntax to represent a state in this riddle:

How many states are there in total?

Let's build the LTS for the riddle:

Solution?

LABELLED TRANSITION SYSTEMS: MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATION

While we draw these as pictures, LTSs can be represented mathematically.

An LTS T is a triple $(States, Actions, \rightarrow)$ consisting of:

A set *States* of states.

A set *Actions* of actions or events.

A set $\rightarrow \subseteq States \times Actions \times States$ of transitions between states labelled by actions (a transition relation).

Example:

$States = \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$

$Actions = \{a, b, c\}$

$\rightarrow = \{(s_1, a, s_2), (s_2, a, s_3), (s_2, b, s_1), (s_3, c, s_3)\}$

	<p>Represent the LTS mathematically:</p>
<p>($X, Y, Z,$ $\{a, b, c\},$ $(X, a, X), (Y, b, Y), (Z, c, Z), (Z, a, X), (X, b, Y)$)</p>	<p>Draw an LTS corresponding to the definition on the left:</p>